

Performances Assessment of Direct Torque Controlled IM Drives Using Fuzzy Logic Control and Space Vector Modulation Strategy

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Abstract : Direct torque control (DTC) is a high performance electric machine closed-loop control technique, which implementation is based on torque and stator flux hysteresis comparators. It is widely known to produce a precise and fast responses in AC drives. However, the classical DTC scheme has a high ripples for both electromagnetic torque and stator flux and a distortion of the stator current. As well it suffer from variable switching frequency. To solve these problems, a lot of modifications in conventional DTC scheme have been made during the last decade. Indeed the DTC based on space vector modulation (SVM) has proved to generate very low torque and flux ripples with constant switching frequency. It also show almost as good dynamic performance as the classical DTC system. On the other hand fuzzy logic is considered as interesting alternative approach for its advantages: analysis close to that user exigencies, ability of nonlinear systems control, best dynamic performances and the inherent quality of robustness. Therefore, two fuzzy direct torque control approaches for induction motor fed by SVM-voltage source inverter are proposed in this paper. Using these two approaches of DTC, the advantages of fuzzy logic control, space vector modulation and direct torque control method are combined. The performance of these DTC schemes is evaluated through digital simulation using Matlab/Simulink package and fuzzy logic tools. Simulation results illustrate the effectiveness and the superiority of the proposed Fuzzy DTC-SVM schemes over the classical DTC.

Keywords : Direct torque control, Fuzzy logic control, Induction motor, Switching frequency, Space vector modulation, Torque and flux ripples.

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